
Steering Self-Evaluation: Interpreting LLM’s Reasoning Across Domains and Languages

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Abstract

Understanding and controlling the reasoning processes of large language models (LLMs) is crucial for their reliable deployment. In this work, we investigate the latent representation of *self-evaluation* behavior - the ability of a model to assess its own reasoning steps - a vital behavior for robust reasoning. Through targeted steering vector computation, we identify a direction within LLM activations that represents this self-evaluation behavior. Crucially, we demonstrate that this steering vector for self-evaluation exhibits remarkable cross-contextual efficacy, working well across different domains (e.g., math and medicine) and languages (e.g., English and Spanish). This suggests that the identified latent direction captures a fundamental, abstract representation of self-evaluation within the LLM’s internal state, offering a promising avenue for interpretable and controllable reasoning across diverse applications.

1. Introduction

Large language models (LLMs) have demonstrated remarkable reasoning capabilities (Reynolds & McDonell, 2021; Wei et al., 2023) in various tasks, yet their reasoning processes often remain opaque. Understanding and controlling these processes is crucial for ensuring the reliable and safe deployment of LLMs, especially in critical applications. However, the high dimensionality of LLM representations and the complex interactions between their internal components make it challenging to exert precise control over specific reasoning behaviors. A key aspect of robust reasoning is the ability of a model to engage in deliberative self-evaluation – to pause, carefully examine its own thought process, and assess the validity and confidence of intermediate reasoning steps, thereby enabling potential error correc-

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Figure 1. Example of self-evaluation behavior. Model double checks its assessment

tion or approach refinement. Figure 1 shows an example of self-evaluation behavior.

Despite its importance, self-evaluation’s latent representation in LLMs is largely unexplored. Prior work (Venhoff et al., 2025) shows steering vectors can induce reasoning mechanisms like uncertainty expression and backtracking, opening the door for controlling LLM reasoning. We build on this to examine if self-evaluation’s representation is a general cognitive mechanism or domain/language-specific.

We demonstrate that a specific direction within LLM activations can be identified and manipulated to elicit or suppress self-evaluative behavior. Furthermore, we show that this “steering vector” exhibits a remarkable domain and language agnosticism, successfully transferring across diverse tasks and linguistic contexts. This suggests that the identified latent direction captures a fundamental, abstract representation of self-evaluation, offering a promising avenue for interpretable and controllable reasoning in LLMs.

In summary, our key contributions are: (1) the definition

and extraction of a steering vector that elicits self-evaluation behavior in the DeepSeek-R1 models, and (2) the demonstration of its remarkable transferability across diverse domains and languages, providing a foundation for controlling and interpreting this behavior in various applications.

2. Methodology

This section details our methodology for defining self-evaluation behavior, computing the self-evaluation steering vector, and applying it to modulate model responses.

2.1. Defining Self-Evaluation Behavior

To identify instances of self-evaluation, we performed a targeted annotation of model-generated text. Self-evaluation was defined as the model’s explicit process of monitoring and assessing its own reasoning steps. This was operationalized by pinpointing the tokens immediately preceding linguistic cues that signal an internal check, uncertainty, or a corrective action. Specifically, we annotated for phrases such as *“but wait”*, *“let me make sure”*, *“let me double check”*, *“I’m reconsidering”*, *“upon reflection”*, and other similar expressions that indicate doubt, verification, or initiation of correction. The annotation process aimed to capture instances where the model deliberates on its own reasoning rather than simply stating a conclusion.

2.2. Computing the Self-Evaluation Steering Vector

We compute the self-evaluation steering vector using a contrastive activation difference approach, a technique that identifies directions in latent space associated with specific behaviors (Arditi et al., 2024). This computation was performed at a chosen layer of the DeepSeek-R1 model.

Positive Set: We generated responses for a set of m input prompts. Within these generated responses, we identified instances of self-evaluation based on our annotation criteria (Section 2.1). For each identified instance, we extracted the hidden state vector, h_{pos_i} , at the token position immediately preceding the self-evaluation trigger phrase. This set of hidden states, representing the model’s internal state prior to self-evaluation, is denoted as $H_{pos} = \{h_{pos_1}, h_{pos_2}, \dots, h_{pos_m}\}$, where i indexes the i -th prompt.

Negative Set: To define a contrasting state, we generated responses for a separate set of n input prompts where self-evaluation was not observed according to our annotation criteria. From these n generated responses, we randomly sampled hidden state vectors, h_{neg_j} , from various token positions. This negative set, representing a baseline internal state, is denoted as $H_{neg} = \{h_{neg_1}, h_{neg_2}, \dots, h_{neg_n}\}$, where j indexes the j -th prompt.

Steering Vector Calculation: The self-evaluation steering vector, V_{se} , was then computed as the difference between the mean of the positive hidden states and the mean of the negative hidden states:

$$V_{se} = \frac{1}{m} \sum_{i=1}^m h_{pos_i} - \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n h_{neg_j} \quad (1)$$

This resulting vector, V_{se} , is hypothesized to represent the direction in the model’s activation space associated with the emergence of self-evaluation.

2.3. Steering the Model’s Behavior

To induce or suppress self-evaluation, we applied the computed steering vector V_{se} to the activations of the chosen layer during model response generation, a method known to effectively modulate LLM behavior (Panickssery et al., 2024; Hegde, 2024). Specifically, the steering vector was added to the hidden state at the token immediately following the input prompt, aiming to influence the subsequent generation. The steered hidden state h' was calculated as:

$$h' = h + \alpha V_{se}$$

where h is the original hidden state, V_{se} is the self-evaluation steering vector, and α is a scalar weight controlling the strength and direction of the effect. A positive value of α was used to induce self-evaluation, while a negative value was used to suppress it. The magnitude of α determines the degree to which the self-evaluation behavior is amplified or diminished.

3. Experiment setup and Results

3.1. Data

We utilized datasets from two distinct domains and in two languages to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the steering vector’s generalizability:

- English Math: The GSM8k dataset (Cobbe et al., 2021) was used for mathematical reasoning questions in English.
- English Medical: The Medical-Reasoning-SFT dataset (Chen et al., 2024) was used for medical reasoning questions in English.
- Spanish Math: A Spanish translation of math word problems¹ was used for mathematical reasoning in Spanish.

¹https://huggingface.co/datasets/juancopi81/orca-math-word-problems-0_10002-spanish

3.2. Model

We conducted our evaluations using distilled versions of DeepSeek-R1 models, which are based on the Qwen architecture. Specifically, we employed smaller, dense models with parameter sizes of 1.5 billion² and 7 billion³.

3.3. Steering Vector Computation

For each training set (English Math, English Medical and Spanish Math), we calculated a self-evaluation steering vector following the methodology described in Section 2.2. We sampled around 100 questions/inputs from each training set, generated responses using the DeepSeek-R1 model, and extracted hidden state vectors to form positive and negative sets. The steering vector was then calculated according to equation 1.

The scalar weight α , controlling steering strength, was empirically tuned for each scenario. We found $\alpha=0.5$ effective for in-domain (English Math) and cross-domain (Math to Medical) evaluations, while $\alpha=0.8$ was more effective for cross-lingual transfer to Spanish Math, potentially due to inter-lingual differences in latent space or linguistic expression.

3.4. Evaluation

The primary evaluation was conducted on samples from the test set of each corresponding dataset. We applied the steering vector computed from the English-Math training data to evaluate its effect on self-evaluation behavior in three scenarios:

- **In-Domain (English-Math):** Applying the English-Math steering vector to English-Math test questions. This scenario serves as a baseline to assess the vector’s efficacy within the training domain.
- **Cross-Domain (Math to Medical):** Applying the English-Math steering vector to English-Medical test questions. This evaluates the vector’s ability to generalize across different subject matter domains within the same language.
- **Cross-Lingual (English to Spanish Math):** Applying the English-Math steering vector to Spanish-Math test questions. This assesses the vector’s capacity to transfer across linguistic boundaries while maintaining the task domain.

For each scenario, we measured the percentage of model-

²<https://huggingface.co/deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-1.5B>

³<https://huggingface.co/deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-R1-Distill-Qwen-7B>

generated responses that exhibited self-evaluation behavior, both with and without the application of the steering vector. Self-evaluation was identified based on the presence of the linguistic cues defined in Section 2.1. The reported results were obtained by applying the steering vector to the final layer of the DeepSeek-R1 model. We focused on the final layer as it is hypothesized to encapsulate higher-level, more abstract representations that are most relevant for controlling complex behaviors (Olah et al., 2017).

3.5. Results

The results of our experiments provide compelling evidence for the cross-domain and cross-lingual transferability of the self-evaluation steering vector. As illustrated in Figure 2, we observed a consistent and statistically significant increase in the prevalence of self-evaluation behavior when the steering vector was applied, compared to the default model across all evaluated scenarios.

- **In-Domain (English Math):** Evaluation on the English Math test set showed a significant increase in self-evaluation behavior when the steering vector was applied. The percentage of responses containing self-evaluation increased from **1%** (default) to **16%** (with steering), demonstrating the effectiveness of our method in isolating and inducing this behavior within the training domain.
- **Cross-Domain (Math to Medical):** Applying the English Math steering vector to the English Medical test set increased self-evaluation (1.5b model: **60%** to **74%**; 7b model: **67%** to **83%**), demonstrating successful cross-domain transfer. The higher baseline self-evaluation in the medical domain suggests a tendency for more self-assessment in high-risk tasks, which the steering vector further enhanced.
- **Cross-Lingual (English to Spanish Math):** Applying the English Math steering vector effectively induced self-evaluation in Spanish Math questions (**1%** to **9%**). The smaller increase compared to English results may reflect differences in optimal α , linguistic expression, or latent space representations between the languages, warranting further investigation into these cross-lingual variations.

3.6. Impact of Steering on Accuracy

We assessed the impact of steering on task accuracy using the GSM8k test set. Both models showed a slight improvement in accuracy with the application of the self-evaluation steering vector (Table 1). While inducing self-evaluation aided in correcting erroneous reasoning steps in a limited number of cases (Figure 5), the model still exhibited failures

Figure 2. Self eval behavior comparison with steering across model sizes

in other instances, potentially due to limitations in the steering vector’s ability to correct deeper flaws in the model’s problem-solving algorithm or its inability to fully address all types of reasoning errors.

4. Practical Implications

The transferability of our self-evaluation steering vector offers practical benefits, particularly for low-resource domains and languages. For example, a vector learned in English legal reasoning could enhance reflective reasoning in Bengali or rare disease diagnosis without requiring new annotations. Furthermore, controlling self-evaluation strength via α allows optimizing LLM output; simple queries can prioritize token efficiency, while high-risk prompts (e.g., medical, financial) can use higher α for enhanced reliability.

5. Related work

This work utilizes steering vectors (Turner et al., 2024) for inference-time control of LLM behavior, a technique within interpretable LLM research. Drawing upon the successful application of steering vectors in prior work to manipulate various model attributes and reasoning mechanisms, our research aligns with studies such as (Arditi et al., 2024), who demonstrated steering refusal behavior, and (Venhoff et al., 2025), who explored the steering of diverse reasoning processes within language models. Building upon this foundation, we focus on the self-evaluation behavior, a critical component of robust reasoning. Furthermore, our investigation into the transferability of the learned self-evaluation steering vector across domains and languages contributes to the broader understanding of representation learning. A significant body of work has leveraged Sparse Autoencoders

(SAEs) to extract interpretable features from LLMs and subsequently steer model behavior by suppressing or amplifying these features. While SAEs, as demonstrated by [(Marks et al., 2025), (Hegde, 2024), (Makelov et al., 2024), (O’Neill & Bui, 2024)] have also shown promise in identifying interpretable features for controlling LLM behavior, they often necessitate substantial data and computational resources for training. In contrast, our work explores the more direct and computationally efficient approach of steering vectors, building upon existing methodologies to target the specific behavior of self-evaluation.

6. Conclusion and Future work

We have shown that self-evaluation behavior in LLMs can be elicited via steering vectors, and that this control generalizes across domains and languages, suggesting an abstract representation. While steering showed promise, further work is needed to enhance its robustness and consistency, explore representational granularity, and study interactions with other reasoning behaviors. Future research will also investigate quantitative evaluation and the context-dependent nature of baseline self-evaluation. Ultimately, this research offers a path towards more interpretable and controllable LLMs, which is crucial for improving their reliability and trustworthiness in real-world applications.

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Figure 3. Example of induced self-evaluation with steering

Table 1. Impact of steering on accuracy of math task.

MODEL	DEFAULT	SELF-EVAL INDUCED
DEEPSEEK-R1-DISTILL-QWEN-1.5B	78.6	79.8
DEEPSEEK-R1-DISTILL-QWEN-7B	81.2	82.7

A. Appendix

A.1. Steering Vector Application Point

We also observed that the timing of the steering vector’s application is crucial. Inducing self-evaluation by applying the vector at the beginning of the response generation (i.e., immediately after the input prompt) was more effective than applying it later in the generation process. This suggests that the steering effect can be overwritten by the model’s inherent tendency to maintain coherence and flow in its output.

A.2. Suppressing Self-evaluation

Complementary to our investigation of inducing self-evaluation, we also explored the effects of suppressing this behavior by applying the steering vector in the negative direction. Our observations revealed a consistent shift in the model’s responses towards a more authoritative and declarative tone compared to its default output. This tendency suggests a potential increase in overconfidence when the inherent self-evaluation mechanisms are dampened, as the model presents information more assertively without exhibiting any internal checks or expressions of uncertainty. Examples illustrating this shift in response style are provided in A.3

A.3. Illustration of steering the model

This appendix provides illustrative examples of the model’s responses when the self-evaluation steering vector is applied for induction and suppression.

Figure 3 presents a representative example of a model response after applying the positive self-evaluation steering vector. Note the inclusion of phrases indicating uncertainty or a deliberate checking process, which were less frequent in the default responses.

Figure 4 shows an example response when the negative self-evaluation steering vector was applied. Observe the more assertive and declarative tone, with a reduced presence of hedging language or explicit self-assessment compared to the default behavior. This illustrates the tendency towards increased authoritativeness when self-evaluation is suppressed.

Figure 4. Example of suppressed self-evaluation with steering

Figure 5. Steering induced deliberate reasoning, resulting in a correct solution.